

1 **On-the-go hyperspectral imaging for the in-field estimation of grape berry soluble solids**
2 **and anthocyanin concentration**

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7 **Abstract**

8 **Background and Aims**

9 Hyperspectral imaging is a powerful tool for fruit composition monitoring, but it is mostly used
10 under laboratory conditions. This work presents a new solution for the non-destructive, in-field
11 prediction of total soluble solids and anthocyanin concentrations in wine grapes in the plant
12 using on-the-go hyperspectral imaging.

13 **Methods and Results**

14 The acquisition of hyperspectral images was carried out under natural illumination conditions
15 using a VIS-NIR hyperspectral camera (400-1000 nm) mounted on an all-terrain vehicle
16 moving at 5 km/h on a commercial Tempranillo vineyard located in La Rioja, Spain.
17 Measurements were taken in four different dates during the grape ripening of season 2017.
18 Grape composition analyses were performed upon the measured grapes for the development of
19 spectral prediction models trained with support vector machines. Total soluble solids models
20 returned determination coefficients R^2 of 0.91 for a 5-fold cross validation (RMSE of 1.358
21 °Brix) and 0.92 for the prediction of external samples (RMSE of 1.274 °Brix). In the case of
22 anthocyanin concentrations, R^2 of 0.72 was achieved for cross validation (RMSE of 0.282 mg/g
23 berry) and 0.83 in prediction (RMSE of 0.211 mg/g berry). Additionally, spatial-temporal
24 variation maps were developed for the four dates displaying the vineyard evolution during grape
25 ripening.

26 **Conclusions**

27 The results support the actual capability of on-the-go hyperspectral imaging for the automated
28 estimation of grape composition parameters directly in the field.

29 **Significance of the Study**

30 The on-the-go hyperspectral imaging methodology described in this study could be considered
31 as a powerful tool for in-field applications in agriculture and vineyard unsupervised monitoring.

32 **Keywords:** svm, plant phenotyping, regression, sensors, proximal sensing

33

34 **1 Introduction**

35

36 Wine quality is directly affected by the compounds present in grapes (Kennedy 2010). The
37 evaluation of grape ripening and quality is often performed by monitoring two important
38 composition parameters: the total soluble solids (TSS) and, in the case of red grapes, the
39 anthocyanin concentrations. TSS refers to the berry's primary metabolite, directly related to the
40 alcoholic strength of the produced wines (Gomes et al. 2017). On the other hand, anthocyanin
41 are phenolic compounds existing in red grape skins (Meléndez et al. 2013) which are
42 responsible for skin tissue pigmentation and red wine color (Boulton 2001). Nowadays, these
43 two grape compositional variables are crucial to determine optimal harvest time, and highly
44 relevant to establish the grape price in many wineries and cooperatives worldwide (Bramley et
45 al. 2011). Being both methods destructive, TSS can be quickly and easily measured using hand-
46 held devices (refractometers), but anthocyanin concentration analysis requires complex wet
47 chemistry methodologies (Iland 2004) that, although provide accurate results, are time
48 consuming, need for specialized personnel and generate chemical waste (Liang et al. 2008). In
49 this context, it may be very valuable for the wine industry to have fast, easy to operate, robust,
50 nondestructive methods to assess the berry composition and its evolution along grape ripening.

51

52 On the other hand, knowledge of the spatial-temporal variation of the TSS and anthocyanin
53 contents within a vineyard may assist decision making regarding sampling and vineyard
54 management, especially if selective harvest is aimed. As a matter of fact, the pattern of spatial
55 variability of grape anthocyanins in a Tempranillo vineyard was shown to change with
56 phenology (Baluja, Diago, Balda, et al. 2012, Baluja, Diago, Goovaerts, et al. 2012). Therefore,
57 to have a truthful picture of the spatial-temporal dynamics of grape composition evolution
58 during ripening in a vineyard, a huge amount of measurements at different timings and spatial
59 positions are required. Unfortunately, the quick in-field measurement of a huge number of
60 samples is very hard for TSS and impossible in the case of analyzing anthocyanin
61 concentrations.

62

63 Several applications can be found in the literature for the in-field manual monitoring of grape
64 composition (Ben Ghozlen et al. 2010, Baluja, Diago, Goovaerts, et al. 2012, Barnaba et al.
65 2014), but these are still time and labor intensive, therefore unsuited for the retrieval of a large
66 and representative amount of data. Also, remote sensing has been attempted as a non-
67 destructive alternative to appraise the spatial variability of grape colour in the vineyard.
68 However, spectral indices were found to be weakly correlated with grape anthocyanins (Lamb
69 et al. 2004). Other authors mounted a chlorophyll-based sensor above the discharge conveyor
70 of a tow-behind harvest machine to determine the anthocyanin content of the harvested fruit at
71 georeferenced spatial positions within the vineyard (Bramley et al. 2011). This enabled the
72 characterization of the vineyard's spatial variability of grape anthocyanins but since assessment
73 was done after the fruit was picked, no possibility of selective harvest decision was provided.

74

75 To overcome these limitations, ground-based on-the-go monitoring can be seen as the next
76 natural step from in-field, manual data collection from the crops. Nevertheless, the on-the-go
77 approach presents several pitfalls that have impeded the transition of successful techniques
78 using manual measurements (Ghozlen et al. 2010) to the continuous monitoring from moving
79 vehicles. Among these restraints, a) the need to “see” the grapes; that is the necessity of having
80 sufficient amount of exposed fruit for the sensor to target fruit instead of material other than
81 grapes; b) the small measuring spot area of many devices (e.g. $\sim 3 \text{ cm}^2$, Fernández-Novales et
82 al. 2017) which make difficult to hit on fruit material; or c) the insufficient signal to noise
83 intensity of many devices, when operated contactless at several cm from the targeted canopy.
84 Moreover, the continuous acquisition of data entails a higher resolution monitoring, and the
85 generation of a big amount of data, which need to be handled and analysed using novel methods.

86

87 In the context of precision agriculture, the relentless development of new sensors, especially
88 within spectral technology, allows for the massive acquisition of high resolution data that could
89 be very useful for the monitoring of crop features, such as grape composition, that can be key
90 in decision-making for selective harvest or winemaking operations. For this reason, the use of
91 on-the-go spectroscopy under field conditions needs to be studied in order to bring its high
92 potential into in-field agricultural applications.

93 In the last years, hyperspectral imaging (HSI) has arisen as a powerful technology for the non-
94 destructive analysis in several agricultural and food quality and safety applications (Sun 2010,

95 Park & Lu 2015). HSI combines into a single tool the features of two different fields: the
96 potential of spectroscopy modeling and the spatial nature of two-dimensional digital imaging.
97 As each pixel in a hyperspectral image provides the full spectrum from the measured target, the
98 capability of this technology for the massive extraction of information from that target raises it
99 as a powerful tool to be employed in the industry. HSI has been widely applied to successfully
100 estimate fruit composition. HSI-based modeling for the TSS prediction has been recently
101 studied in grape berries (Gomes et al. 2017, Piazzolla et al. 2017), apple (Ma et al. 2017, Mo et
102 al. 2017, Tian et al. 2018) or mango (Rungpichayapichet et al. 2017), while the anthocyanin
103 concentrations has been predicted also in grape berries (Diago et al. 2016, Martínez-Sandoval
104 et al. 2016, Zhang et al. 2017), mulberry (Huang et al. 2017) or raspberry (Rodríguez-Pulido et
105 al. 2017). Nevertheless, all these works (and almost every other fruit-related studies using HSI)
106 have one important factor in common: all they were performed in laboratory, under controlled
107 conditions, such as illumination, sample positioning and temperature, among others. It is thus
108 a natural next stage to study how a HSI system behaves when it is deployed in the field, but
109 great challenges arise with this apparently small step. Different ambient conditions are a
110 constant during in-field experiments, and also target's location and position are non-constant
111 features either. For this reason, there is room for many potential applications of HSI in the field,
112 and for studying new methodologies for the automated acquisition and processing of
113 hyperspectral images. Very few works can be found in the literature using in-field HSI (Deery
114 et al. 2014, Williams et al. 2017), but even on-the-go approaches in robotics has been reported
115 (Underwood et al. 2017, Wendel & Underwood 2017). Given the demonstrated potential of HSI
116 for the prediction of grape composition parameters, the addition of a higher level of vineyard
117 monitoring that can be obtained by on-the-go measurements opens a new frontier in precision
118 viticulture, as high-resolution information can be obtained, processed and mapped using
119 automated platforms.

120 For these reasons, the development of a new methodology for the in-field monitoring of grape
121 composition parameters is a desirable next step in the context of precision viticulture and wine
122 decision making, and new technologies makes this an attainable objective. Therefore, the goal
123 of this work was the in-field estimation and mapping of two important grape composition
124 parameters, TSS and anthocyanin concentrations, with the clusters still in the plants, using non-
125 destructive on-the-go hyperspectral imaging.

126

127 **2 Materials and methods**

128

129 The design of the study was split into three major stages (Fig. 1). In the first one, the in-field
130 experiments were carried out, comprising the on-the-go HSI image acquisition and the
131 collection and chemical analyses of the imaged grape samples. In the second stage, the
132 hyperspectral images were processed (for the automated extraction of grape berry spectra) and
133 the datasets generated. In the last stage, the dataset was used as input for the training of different
134 prediction models using machine learning algorithms and use for the generation of different
135 maps.

136

137 **2.1 In-field experiments**

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139 **2.1.1 Experimental layout**

140

141 The experiment was performed in a 0.7 ha commercial vineyard located in Álbalos, La Rioja,
142 Spain (Lat. 42° 34' 45.7", Long. -2° 42' 27.78", Alt. 628 m). Grapevines of Tempranillo (*Vitis*
143 *vinifera* L.) variety were planted in 2010, on rootstock R-110 and trained to a vertically shoot-
144 positioned (VSP) trellis system. The rows in the vineyard had a Northeast-Southwest
145 orientation, and 2.20×1.00 meters inter and intra row distances. Three different equally-
146 distanced rows were selected and, within each one of them, 12 blocks with five plants each
147 (five meters per block) were chosen for the spectral and grape berry analyses (a total of 36
148 blocks). Hyperspectral measurements were performed on the east side of the canopy, which
149 was defoliated on the basal zone. In order to modeling all different stages of ripening, data
150 acquisition was carried out during four dates from veraison to harvest, in different phenological
151 stages—according to the modified Eichhorn and Lorenz system (Coombe 1995)—during
152 season 2017: 11 August, stage 36; 24 August, stage 37; 18 September, stage 38; and 28
153 September, stage 38. Therefore, the total number of blocks that were measured throughout the
154 entire experiment was 144 (36 blocks per date, four different dates).

155 Hyperspectral images were acquired on-the-go using a push broom Resonon Pika L VNIR
156 hyperspectral imaging camera (Resonon, Inc., Bozeman, MA, USA) that was installed on an
157 all-terrain vehicle ATV, Fig 2) (Trail Boss 330, Polaris Industries, MN, USA) and connected

158 to an industrial computer. The camera's spectral resolution was 2.1 nm (300 bands from 400 to
159 1000 nm), with 300 pixels of spatial resolution. An 8 mm focal length lens was used, pointed
160 to the canopy on a lateral point of view at 2.0 m of distance, that cast a vertical recording line
161 upon the plants of 1.32 m (field of view of 36.5°). The recording line covered the whole vine
162 canopy, including the fruiting zone (Fig. 2). The 36 measurements per day (one for each block)
163 were performed on the southeast canopy side, between 10:00 and 14:00, under the natural
164 illumination from the sun only. To test the HSI methodology under reproducible scenarios (*i.e.*,
165 other different kinds of terrestrial vehicles), no specific mechanical compensation was applied
166 for terrain irregularities corrections other than vehicle's own suspension. Nevertheless, the
167 distance between camera and plants made it certain that the scene acquired by the sensor always
168 covered the whole plants (and, therefore, the grape bunches).

169 To take into account the naturally variable illumination conditions, the values for the camera
170 configuration parameters (integration time and frames per seconds, FPS) were adapted for each
171 block measurement, depending on the light intensity, in order to find the best trade-off between
172 acceptable image composition, enough spectral intensity and the prevention of saturation. FPS
173 ranged from 50 (taking one frame each 20 milliseconds) at the beginning of the season to 40 at
174 the end (one frame each 25 milliseconds). Prior to the block's hyperspectral measurement, a
175 Spectralon® white reference (a surface with a reflectance over 95%) was manually presented
176 to the camera and recorded simulating the same position and distance than to the canopy. A
177 dark current measurement was also performed, to obtain the inherent electronic noise. After
178 this, the block was imaged on-the-go at a constant speed of 5 km/h, composing a hyperspectral
179 image by push broom scanning (Fig. 2) with an average number of scanlines (columns) of 710,
180 with 900 pixels each one. On average, a total of 639,000 pixels (*i.e.*, spectra) per block were
181 acquired.

182 The spectral light intensity values collected by the camera were translated into reflectance (R):

183
$$R = \frac{G(\lambda) - D(\lambda)}{W(\lambda) - D(\lambda)}$$

184 where λ is a wavelength, G is the intensity of the light reflected by the canopy, W is the intensity
185 of the light coming from the white reference, and D is the dark current. The reflectance was
186 then converted into absorbance ($\log(1/R)$). To prevent the noise that is commonly found in the
187 tails of a spectral signal, the first 10 bands and the last 50 ones were discarded, thus obtaining
188 spectra that comprised 240 bands (from 410 to 921 nm).

189 Hyperspectral images were georeferenced using a GPS receiver Ag Leader 6500 (Ag Leader
190 Technology, Inc., Ames, IA, USA) with RTK correction installed on the ATV.

191

192 **2.1.2 Analysis of grape composition**

193

194 At each measuring date, immediately after the HSI of each block, all the exposed clusters were
195 identified and, from them, portions of 10-15 visible berries were manually picked, bagged and
196 labeled for their subsequent chemical analysis. On average, a total of 200 grape berries per
197 block were collected each date. The closed bags that contained the berries were then transported
198 in portable refrigerators to the laboratory and stored in a freezer at -20 °C until chemical
199 analysis.

200 Two different grape berry composition parameters were measured: the total soluble solid (TSS)
201 and total anthocyanin concentrations. Fruits were thawed overnight (in a cold room at 4°C)
202 before grape composition analysis. For each sample, a subsample of 100 berries was hand
203 crushed and filtered. The TSS concentration was determined using a temperature compensating
204 digital refractometer Quick-Brix 60 (Mettler Toledo, LLC, Columbus, OH, USA), expressed as
205 °Brix. The remaining berry sub-sample was homogenized using a high-performance disperser
206 T25 Ultra-Turrax (IKA, Staufen, Germany) at high speed (14,000 rpm for 60 s). Afterwards,
207 anthocyanin concentrations were measured (Iland 2004) and expressed as mg per gram of berry
208 mass.

209

210 **2.2 Image processing**

211

212 **2.2.1 Processing of hyperspectral images**

213

214 From each hyperspectral image, it was needed to automatically obtain all the spectra belonging
215 to grape clusters. To do this, prior to the automated image processing, a grape reference
216 spectrum was obtained by manually selecting grape spectra from all the images (regions of
217 approximately 200 spectra) and then averaging them. With this signature spectrum (that was
218 also pre-processed with a Savitzky-Golay smoothing and derivative (Savitzky & Golay 1964)),
219 the following described algorithm was coded using Python 3.6.1:

220 Defining I as the original hyperspectral image and C an empty matrix with the same width and
221 height than I . Each one of the bins of C (with coordinates x, y) is filled with the determination
222 coefficient from the correlation analysis between each one of the pixels of I in the same position
223 (e.g., spectra in the x, y coordinates) and the grape signature spectra. The similarity of each
224 pixel (spectrum) from I with the grape signature spectra is thus represented as a R^2 value, and
225 a correlation matrix C is built with them. After a two-dimensional Gaussian smoothing to C
226 (with σ set to 1.0), all the pixels from C that surpass the 0.75 mark are identified as grape spectra
227 and averaged (the 0.75 value was manually selected after intensive supervised review of the
228 results of the processing of several hyperspectral images). This average is thus considered as
229 the image (block) grape average spectrum. For more details, the reader is referred to the
230 pseudocode description of this algorithm included as supplementary material.

231 Fig. 3 exemplifies the output of this algorithm. In (a), the original hyperspectral image is
232 displayed with the RGB channels, while in (b), its correlation matrix C after the Gaussian
233 smoothing is shown. Finally, the selected grape pixels (those from C whose R^2 are equal or
234 greater than 0.75) are segmented in (c).

235 In a small proportion of hyperspectral images, a very small number of pixels identified as grape
236 had a spectral shape with higher intensity than the white reference's. This was due to incident
237 sunlight that was directly reflected into the camera's sensor, hence returning a reflectance value
238 over 1.0 in some wavelengths. These pixels were therefore discarded from the final spectra
239 averaging.

240

241 **2.2.2 Generation of the dataset**

242

243 After the grape berry spectra and the chemical parameters were obtained for each block, they
244 were used to build the dataset, in which each spectrum was linked with its corresponding
245 composition parameters. Having 36 blocks and four different measurement dates, the dataset
246 comprised a total of 144 samples, covering all the measurement dates. From this, train and test
247 subsets were built in an 80-20 ratio respectively by randomly extracting a 20% of samples per
248 date, making up a train set of 115 samples and a test set of 29 samples.

249

250 **2.3 Development of prediction models**

251

252 **2.3.1 Machine learning modeling**

253

254 Several machine learning algorithms were tested for modeling, based on authors' experience
255 and criteria, and Epsilon-Support vector machines (ϵ -SVMs) were finally used for the training
256 of the regression models due to its better performance statistics. The input independent variables
257 X were the spectra ($|X| = 240$, the number of spectral bands), pre-processed with standard normal
258 variate (Barnes et al. 1989) and Savitzky-Golay filter (second-grade derivative, window size of
259 15), while the TSS and anthocyanin concentrations were used as dependent variables y , each
260 one for the training of two different models. In both cases, a radial basis function kernel was
261 used, with $\epsilon = 0.1$ and $\gamma = 0.00417 (1/|X|)$. The penalty parameter C was set to 100 in the case
262 of TSS and 30 for anthocyanin concentrations. The performance of SVM for the train test was
263 evaluated using a 5-fold cross validation. The prediction results were obtained by training a
264 model with all the samples from the train test and predicting the samples from the test set. All
265 the models were developed using the Epsilon-Support vector regression implementation in
266 scikit-learn 0.18.1 (Pedregosa et al. 2011).

267

268 **2.3.2 Spatio-temporal mapping**

269

270 The usefulness of on-the-go HSI for the monitoring of grape composition within a vineyard
271 was illustrated by developing TSS and anthocyanin concentrations prediction maps from the
272 commercial vineyard in which the experiments were performed during the ripening period.
273 Interpolation maps were generated using multilevel b-spline interpolation (Lee et al. 1997)
274 implemented in QGIS 2.19 (Free Software Foundation, Boston, MA, USA).

275

276 **3 Results**

277

278 **3.1 Grape composition variation**

279

280 The histograms for TSS and anthocyanin concentrations on each experimental date are
281 displayed in Fig. 4, also summarizing the main statistical information about the variation of
282 these two compositional parameters.

283 TSS yielded a wide range from 10.7 °Brix (expected value for grapes at mid-ripening
284 phenological stage) to 25.2 °Brix, indicating that the grapes reached full maturity. The mean
285 and standard deviation values also indicated a wide variability within the measured TSS values.
286 The results from the anthocyanin analyses demonstrated that the same behavior was observed
287 for this parameter, with values ranging from lower values of 0.05 (at veraison, when
288 anthocyanin synthesis has not yet been triggered in all berries) to 2.01 mg/g berry at harvest.
289 The mean values increased throughout the season, while the standard deviations widened until
290 September.

291 Attending to the shape of the histograms, as expected for both parameters, the gross of their
292 values per date increased as season evolved. For TSS, very similar values were found in the
293 two last dates, indicating a final stage in maturity at which TSS no longer increases by
294 physiological ripening process. In the case of the anthocyanin concentrations, the values for the
295 first date stayed within a limited mg/g berry range, but this range became wider in the next three
296 dates, a behavior that could correspond to an asynchronous ripening of the fruit (internal
297 variability).

298

299 **3.2 Prediction models and mapping**

300

301 The cross-validation and prediction results of the total soluble solids models are plot in Fig. 5.
302 The 5-fold cross validation (Fig. 5(a)) yielded a determination coefficient R^2 of 0.91, with a
303 root mean squared error (RMSE) of 1.358 °Brix. The regression line can be found almost
304 exactly over the 1:1 line, and a good distribution of the samples along it was observed. The
305 prediction results (Fig. 5(b)) cast comparable values for both R^2 (0.92) and RMSE (1.274 °Brix).

306 Fig. 6 gathers the regression plots from the cross validation and prediction models for the berry
307 anthocyanin concentrations. Fig. 6(a) displays a cross validation R^2 of 0.72, while the prediction
308 results (Fig. 6(b)) yielded a larger determination coefficient of 0.83. For the first case, the
309 RMSE value was 0.282 mg/g berry, but, in Fig. 6(b), the lower number of samples and their
310 concentrated locations reduced the RMSE value to 0.211 mg/g berry.

311 In Fig. 7, the evolution of TSS and anthocyanin concentrations are displayed in eight prediction
312 maps, one per date and grape composition parameter, for the commercial vineyard plot in which
313 the experiments were carried out. The evolution of TSS (Fig. 7) remained steady throughout
314 the different maturity stages, and a large gap can be found between 24 August and 18
315 September. The maximum values were reached in the latter, and in the last date only a slight
316 increase in °Brix was found. The south corner of the vineyard plot showed the quickest ripening
317 speed.

318 In the case of the anthocyanin concentrations, big gaps were present between the four dates,
319 from little variation (from 0.15 to 0.35 mg/g berry) on 11 August, to a plot with higher
320 anthocyanin concentrations and variability on 28 September.

321

322 **3.3 Computational cost**

323

324 The processing of 36 hyperspectral images using the described algorithm in section 2.2.1 took,
325 per date, an average of 5 hours and 35 minutes in an Intel® Core™ i7-5820K CPU with 16 GB
326 of RAM (no thread optimization). Taking into account that each image was composed of
327 approximately 710 scanlines (columns), the calculations result in an average processing time
328 of 0.79 s per column, while the prediction of a single sample using a trained SVM model took
329 0.05 s. With all this, on a real-time scenario, the processing and prediction of a hyperspectral
330 scanline would take less than a second.

331

332 **4 Discussion**

333

334 The present work has displayed a new solution for the non-destructive, in-field estimation of
335 grape composition using on-the-go hyperspectral imaging in a commercial vineyard. These
336 results have demonstrated not only the suitability of hyperspectral cameras for the estimation
337 of two important grape composition parameters, but the actual possibility of bringing this kind
338 of devices from in-door to the field. HSI is a technology originally conceived to be employed
339 in laboratories or in-door environments, in which the environmental conditions can be
340 completely controlled, in terms of illumination, temperature, sample and camera stability, etc.
341 Nevertheless, its passage to the field requires the overcoming of the changing conditions caused

342 by these factors. Additionally, in this work, the on-the-go acquisition of hyperspectral images
343 successfully carried out, by means of a motorized platform at agricultural speeds (5 km/h). The
344 use of a mobile vehicle brings specific circumstances that are not contemplated in in-door
345 conditions (or even outdoor ones, but with static measurements), such as irregularities in the
346 terrain, motor vibrations, slight but constant differences in the distance between the lens and
347 the target, heterogeneous speed, etc. The presented results, one of the first attempts---and, to
348 the best of our knowledge, the first one in grapevine---validate a feasible methodology for the
349 development of fruitful prediction models using a hyperspectral camera within all the
350 mentioned conditions. This opens a wide number of options for the monitoring of a vineyard,
351 by different mobile platforms.

352 The methodologies studied in this work are prone to be deployed on specific, man-driven
353 platforms (like the ATV used), agricultural vehicles operating upon the crops, or even using
354 autonomous phenotyping and monitoring platforms (*i.e.*, agricultural robots). This last option
355 also requires an important step of automation in the image computation, something that can be
356 achieved when dealing with hyperspectral images, as the methodology described in section
357 2.2.1 (the precise selection of grape spectra and the prediction of their composition value) could
358 be directly translated even into a robot. A collection of grape spectral could be preloaded into
359 the platform's system, limiting the manual grape sample spectra collection to, for example,
360 once per season. Therefore, along with a pretrained model, the prediction of grape composition
361 could be fully automated during plot monitoring by the platform. Some works in the literature
362 have proven that HSI can be performed under field conditions (Williams et al. 2017) and even
363 on-the-go (Deery et al. 2014, Underwood et al. 2017, Wendel & Underwood 2017). It could be
364 possible the development of a complete integration between HSI sensors, GPS and computing
365 into a single platform capable of performing real-time assessment in the vineyard. Some recent
366 examples have been published using HSI devices with integrated GPS (Sandino et al. 2018,
367 Vanegas et al. 2018). This scheme is valid for its integration within current viticulture-related
368 work trends, and it can be possible to take advantage of working agricultural vehicles already
369 deployed and to install a HSI monitoring system on them. The exposed outcomes of in-field,
370 on-the-go HSI open new windows for its usage in many other different crops, using similar
371 techniques for spectral segmentation and prediction model training. Additionally, and taking
372 advantage of HSI's extra spatial dimensions, the use of this technology is not limited for the
373 automatic monitoring of just the fruit, but also other organs at the same time (*e.g.*, leaves or
374 stems).

375 Several works have demonstrated that the monitoring of grape composition throughout the
376 ripening is a feasible goal using spectroscopic technologies (Larrain et al. 2008, Cao et al. 2010,
377 González-Caballero et al. 2010, Bellincontro et al. 2011, Barnaba et al. 2014, Musingarabwi et
378 al. 2016), performed mostly under laboratory conditions. In-field grape composition monitoring
379 has been reported in previous works using spectroscopy, but from contact, discrete
380 measurements using portable manual devices. A portable NIR spectrophotometer was used for
381 the estimation of TSS under field conditions (Urraca et al. 2016), reporting prediction RMSE
382 values of 1.68 °Brix and 10-fold cross validation laboratory R^2 up to 0.90 (with an RMSE of
383 1.47 °Brix). These results were slightly lower than those from the present study, but still
384 comparable, as a portable device can be easily deployed in the field. Nevertheless, clear
385 advantages of on-the-go HSI can be found, as the combination of fastest acquisition time and
386 larger number of samples covered makes the detailed monitoring of a whole vineyard plot a
387 more feasible goal. Staying on this subject, HSI has been previously proven to be an accurate
388 tool for TSS and anthocyanin concentrations estimation under laboratory conditions. Regarding
389 TSS, several works have reported prediction R^2 values from 0.88 to 0.93 (RMSEs of 0.950 and
390 0.930 °Brix, respectively) (Gomes et al. 2017, Piazzolla et al. 2017). Similar performance values
391 were obtained for °Brix prediction using the on-the-go approach described in this study,
392 possibly explained by the fact that the same VIS-NIR spectral region (400-1000 nm) was used.
393 Regarding the estimation of grape anthocyanin concentrations, HSI has been widely employed
394 for this goal (Diago et al. 2016, Martínez-Sandoval et al. 2016, Zhang et al. 2017). The reported
395 R^2 values range from 0.72 up to 0.93, in line with the ones presented in this study. It must be
396 highlighted that, if the prediction models developed in this work can be deemed to be solid and
397 reliable, it is also because the in-field spectral information used for their training came from
398 four different dates and phenological stages. Pre-veraison data acquisition was considered, but
399 rapidly discarded since biosynthesis or changes in composition of most relevant grape berry
400 compounds start at veraison. Moreover, it is at this stage when the vine's vegetative growth
401 stops, therefore the most prominent sinks in the plant are the berries, hence the changes in their
402 composition. From a practical perspective (not scientifically speaking) there is no interest in
403 assessing the berry composition prior to veraison, as no utilization for winemaking can be done
404 at those early stages. For these reasons, including data from dates before veraison would not
405 improve results, nor would it be useful for vineyard monitoring. However, the training with
406 data from different post-veraison phenological phases made thus possible for the models to
407 acquire the capability of monitoring the evolution and spatial distribution of total soluble solids
408 and anthocyanin concentrations at different moments along grape ripening. This feature

409 increases the application value of the models developed using the described methodology in
410 commercial and industrial environments.

411 The on-the-go estimation of important grape composition parameters brings a new tool for
412 many actors in grapevine growing and wine industry. The developed HSI methodology has
413 proven to overcome two of the three main limitations for on-the-go grape monitoring, that is a
414 larger spot size of measurement (basically all fruit exposed area is measured) and the sufficient
415 signal to noise ratio. Regarding the need to “see the fruit”, some level of cluster exposure in
416 undoubtedly required, but partial basal defoliation of the morning side mainly, is a common
417 practice in many regions worldwide to improve cluster exposure and air circulation (Smart et
418 al. 1991).

419 The mapping of a whole vineyard plot perfectly fits with the goal of precision viticulture, in the
420 current sustainability context, as the accurate monitoring and characterization of heterogeneous
421 zones carries a high amount of useful information that could help in the decision-making
422 process. TSS estimation is directly related to the monitoring of grape ripening, allowing to take
423 precise decisions on when and where to harvest, while anthocyanin concentrations could for
424 example help to characterize zones of different grape qualities, assigning them to different
425 wine-making processes. As exposed in Fig. 7, the monitoring and mapping of composition
426 parameters lets the visualization of their spatial distribution within the field. In this case, at each
427 measured stage during grape ripening, the plotted results from this methodology can be used as
428 a powerful diagnostic tool, improving and optimizing the decision-making capacities.

429

430 **5 Conclusions**

431

432 This work presents the potential of in-field on-the-go hyperspectral imaging for the monitoring
433 of grape composition in a commercial vineyard. The results obtained from the spectral models
434 trained with support vector machines demonstrates that it is possible to deploy a hyperspectral
435 camera from the laboratory to the field, that can acquire high resolution information of large
436 areas in a fast, unsupervised approach. A HSI system could thus be attached to agricultural
437 machinery or even robotics. Likewise, mapping of grape composition during different
438 phenological stages in a season were developed, maps that provide the farmer with information
439 that could be very useful in the decision making process. This work is also one of the few new
440 applications of on-the-go HSI under field conditions, and possibly the first one in grapevine.

441

442 **6 References**

443

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565

566 **Figure legends**

567

568 **Fig 1** Design of the study, split into three major stages: in-field experiments, processing of the images
569 and development of prediction models.

570

571

572 **Fig 2** On-the-go hyperspectral imaging with a camera mounted on an ATV at 5 km/h. Images of the
573 entire vine canopy were obtained from the ATV's motion, by push-broom scanning, and used for the
574 estimation of grape composition.

575

576

577 **Fig 3** (a) Hyperspectral image from a block in RGB channels (histogram normalized for the sake of
 578 illustration). (b) Correlation matrix with R^2 values between the pixel spectrum and a grape reference
 579 spectrum. A Gaussian smoothing was applied with $\sigma = 1.0$. (c) Image with segmented grape pixels
 580 (pixels in (b) whose $R^2 \geq 0.75$). All the images were stretched in the horizontal axis for aesthetic
 581 purposes.

582

583

584 **Fig 4** Histograms for total soluble solids (left column) and anthocyanin concentrations (right column)

585 for each one of the experimental dates on 2017. SD: standard deviation.

587

588 **Fig 5** Regression plot for 5-fold cross validation (a) and prediction results (b) for the total soluble solids
 589 models. Solid closed line segment refers to the regression line of the samples, while the dotted open line
 590 segment represents the 1:1 trend. RMSE: root mean squared error (in °Brix).

591

592

593 **Fig 6** Regression plot for 5-fold cross validation (a) and prediction results (b) for the anthocyanins
 594 concentrations models. Solid closed line segment refers to the regression line of the samples, while the
 595 dotted open line segment represents the 1:1 trend. RMSE: root mean squared error (in mg/g berry).

596

597

598 **Fig 7** Prediction maps for grape total soluble solids (a) and anthocyanin concentrations (b) displaying
 599 the evolution of both parameters for the four different dates during grape ripening.